

EFFECT OF MULTIMEDIA MEDIA ON EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation: The article talks about the introduction of multimedia technologies into the educational process. In recent years, multimedia technology has entered the educational field and has had a significant impact on the methodology of teaching information and the knowledge of students in general. The traditional method has been used in our educational institutions for decades, but now, under the influence of multimedia technologies, the fundamental mode and concepts of student education are changing. As a result, the use of multimedia technologies in education brings the educational process of students to a higher, innovative level.

Key words: multimedia technology, media education, multimedia educational tools.

Introduction.

Universities have the task of preparing a comprehensively developed person, a specialist with flexible thinking, capable of successfully performing various professional tasks, and ready to acquire new knowledge independently throughout his life. Therefore, an effective, high-quality personnel training system at a new stage, which is closely related to the improvement of the content of education and personnel training, the introduction of media education into the pedagogical process, the updating of educational and methodological documents, the training and qualification of personnel development is necessary. The technical base, the use of media-educational technologies in the training of pedagogical personnel, etc.

It can also be mentioned that the abundance of information today makes the classes interesting and meaningful. One of the ways to collect data and present them in an easy way is to prepare infographic materials. For example, we can make an infographic slide for a lesson, or present it in the form of a document, poster, or make a short video clip. To do this, we need to be familiar with practical programs. Nowadays, not having access to educational technologies is like a student who does not know how to read and write. It is necessary for every teacher to have the skills of documenting and preparing presentations in computer applications, even at the minimum level. Only after that he can use the multimedia possibilities. The analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature shows that multimedia affects a person by satisfying his cognitive needs (getting comprehensive information about the world), affective (formation of new, emotional, as well as aesthetic experiences); personal integration (increasing contacts with other members of society), reducing tension (providing entertainment and leisure activities). Now there is no doubt about the influence of mass media on the receivers, but the degree of its intensity varies.

An important condition for the implementation and implementation of multimedia technologies in the educational process is the presence of specially equipped classrooms

equipped with a multimedia projector, a computer for the teacher, a screen or a multimedia board and an environment in which the educational process is carried out (computer classrooms, libraries, media libraries, Internet access, etc.). Currently, the issue of equipping universities with ready-made multimedia educational materials created by university employees or other developers has become urgent.

In recent years, multimedia technology has entered the educational field and has had a significant impact on the methodology of teaching information and the knowledge of students in general. The classical method has been used in our educational institutions for decades, but now, under the influence of multimedia technologies, the fundamental mode and concepts of student education are changing. As a result, the use of multimedia technologies in education brings the educational process of students to a higher, innovative level.

Multimedia is designed to appeal to multiple senses. A multimedia learning environment facilitates and enhances learning. Real or virtual images, texts, sounds, graphics and pictures enriched with multimedia technologies in the computer environment help to prepare qualified educational programs. Various media such as graphics, video, animation and sound, when presented together, are believed to facilitate and enhance learning by differentiating the learning environment.

Multimedia technologies are a powerful tool for creating and presenting multi-level scientific ideas. By using multimedia technologies in lectures, it increases the interest of students and keeps them active in presenting the material. If the teacher taught in the classical format, that is, if he did not have multimedia technologies, he would not have achieved such success.

Learning with the help of multimedia technologies is one of the factors of successful education, which gives students the confidence to achieve good results. With the help of multimedia tools, information can be presented in the form of text, images, sound and animation. Multimedia information resources consist of animated, audio and video information.

Scientists M. Sanger, T. Grinbow, R. Mitchell, D. Gabel and others pay attention to the fact that class activities are intended not only to form knowledge, but also to teach students to apply it in practice. Creating a knowledge base is important to provide a conducive learning environment. Teachers should create a diagram to represent the student's level of knowledge and apply this idea to the curriculum so that the student can receive multimedia information to guide learning using the Internet.

According to UNESCO documents, media education is the teaching of theoretical and practical skills in mastering modern mass communication tools, pedagogical theory and structure of a specific field in practice. Media education should be distinguished from mass communication as a source of support for educational materials in other fields. The first stage of media education dates back to the 60s and 70s, the second stage to the 80s, the third stage called multimedia (end of the 90s) is associated with the rapid development of computer technology. The terms "multimedia in education" began to be actively used in scientific circles in the late 90s.

At the beginning of the 21st century, scientists interpreted multimedia as a unique "medium" that optimizes the formation of a modern person's personality and affects his daily activities. While most researchers consider multimedia as a powerful means of information (communication and culture), some experts consider it a serious threat to children, taking

into account the achievements of the globalization era.

Based on comprehensive reflection of scientific literature, it has been proven that multimedia is not only informational, but also communicative resources that influence society and help to effectively organize the education and training process. The scope of the application of multimedia in education has expanded significantly: from the use of multimedia technologies in the creation of educational programs to the development of a holistic concept of the construction of educational programs in the field of multimedia, the training of university-level personnel in a certain direction and new educational formation of weapons.

Multimedia is very useful and effective in education due to its interactivity, flexibility and integration of different media that supports learning, takes into account individual differences among students and increases their motivation.

Although it is being implemented gradually, the introduction of multimedia educational tools is inevitable. Taking into account the rapid development of multimedia technologies, their introduction into the educational process should be fast. According to J. Ellsworth, it is necessary to find an innovative approach to optimize the introduction of multimedia technologies in education. The educational community must find ways to facilitate the spread of information technology in educational institutions.

However, there are many aspects to consider when using multimedia in education. Although multimedia is available worldwide, access to learning materials and computing equipment varies from country to country.

The use of multimedia by students should be supported by highly qualified teachers. They should guide students through the learning process and provide them with appropriate and effective learning strategies. Like the use of textbooks, the use of multimedia learning strategies of teaching, in which the role of the teacher is not only that of an informant, but also that of a guide, facilitator and facilitator. Must explain and teach students how to use multimedia learning strategies.

Multimedia technologies enable the integration of various multimedia information in a meaningful and harmonious way and help to present knowledge in various formats, including:

- Provides access to images, including scanned photographs, drawings, maps and slides;
- Sounds, e.g. sound, noise and music recordings;
- Video, including complex video effects and animation simulation;
- Animation and simulations;
- Discussions among students (social networks, online discussions, blogs, etc.).

Presentations accompanied by beautiful images or animations can be more engaging than lectures, supplementing the material being presented and keeping learners emotionally engaged. Multimedia can have many educational benefits. Some students prefer to learn by reading, others by listening or watching videos, etc. In addition, the use of multimedia provides different ways of working - students can independently decide how to learn the material, as well as how to use it interactively and with friends.

Students can learn their learning process according to their abilities and preferences. They can work according to their interests, repeat the lesson process as much as they want to reduce the inconvenience of the learning results.

Multimedia applications can be used to facilitate group work. Small groups of students can work together through multimedia applications - to learn from each other as well as to improve their communication skills.

The use of multimedia technologies in the educational process allows the transition from a passive method of educational activity to an active one, in which the student acts as the main participant in the educational process. When choosing multimedia training manuals, the teacher should take into account the uniqueness of a specific educational subject, ensure the uniqueness of the subject, its conceptual apparatus, and the unique features of the methods of studying its laws. Multimedia technologies should correspond to the goals and tasks of the educational course and be organic components of the educational process.

Currently, various aspects of the use of multimedia technologies in education are being actively studied, it is necessary to distinguish technical and psychological-pedagogical features of multimedia technologies, and to use them purposefully and effectively in the educational process of secondary and higher schools. Most teachers and psychologists say that modern information technologies, in particular, multimedia, allow students to use non-traditional sources of information, a fundamentally new way of teaching using conceptual and mathematical modeling of phenomena and processes that increases educational efficiency. helps to implement forms and methods.

The work of domestic and foreign scientists, teachers and psychologists shows that the use of multimedia optimizes the solution of didactic issues with great educational impact, can become a means of increasing learning efficiency, significantly reduces time, significantly deepens the scope and expands. At the same time, in the field of pedagogy and especially in the practice of local teaching, it should be noted that computer teaching tools, especially multimedia capabilities, are not always correctly evaluated. This is primarily due to the complexity and insufficient theoretical development of the concept of "multimedia" as a didactic tool.

In conclusion, we emphasize that the continuous use of multimedia tools in the educational process has a profound effect on the student's development. At the present stage, the important task of the university is to humanize the educational process, to form the individuality of students, and to form a high information culture. This requires the teacher to have knowledge and skills in the field of using the latest pedagogical technologies, to master the advanced methods and tools of modern science. At the same time, the results of foreign and domestic studies do not always confirm the definite advantages of using computer technologies in the modern educational process.

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